

Historical exploitation and widespread decline of blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*) bed habitat in Scotland

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ABSTRACT

Historical records reveal that sustained anthropogenic exploitation drove widespread decline of blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*) bed habitat in Scotland by the early 20th century. We synthesised >200 archival records published between 1760 and 1970 and over a century of landings data to reconstruct the historical distribution, extent and status of Scottish mussel beds, and document the history and trajectory of the mussel and associated line fishing industries. Archival evidence enabled the mapping of 124 historical beds at a resolution of 5 km²; by the early 1900s, 51 % were reported as nearly or entirely exhausted or destroyed. Only one source described localised recovery in the 1960s, years after exploitation ceased. Spatial extent data were available for 31 % of the historical mussel beds and for three mussel fishing areas, representing ~1800 ha and ~5600 ha respectively. From at least the 16th century, mussels were highly sought after and intensively harvested primarily for line-fishing bait. Across the 1800s, accelerated exploitation compounded by additional stressors, viz. pollution, trawling, trampling, predation and smothering, drove widespread degradation of mussel bed habitat and likely reduced ecosystem resilience, with lasting ecological and socio-economic consequences. Mussel landings exceeded 10,000 tonnes in the late 19th century but significantly declined thereafter and ceased entirely by 2004- mirroring significant declines in line fishing landings. Reduced mussel bait availability, rising competition with trawlers and alternative job opportunities were key drivers. This unique empirical record provides valuable context for contemporary habitat restoration efforts by identifying historical locations and extents of a now much reduced and threatened habitat.

1. Introduction

Throughout history, estuaries and coastlines have been focal points for human settlement (Lotze et al., 2006). These highly productive environments have supported human societies for thousands of years, supplying essential commodities such as food and water, and delivering a wide range of ecosystem and cultural services, including flood and erosion control, storm protection, shoreline stabilisation, recreation and transportation (Airoldi and Beck, 2007; Bailey, 2004; Barbier, 2017; Erlandson and Rick, 2010; Kaiser and Williams, 2011; Noble et al., 2018). Biogenic habitats are important features of estuarine and coastal environments; these structures are created by aggregations of low-trophic level foundation species that settle on mixed sediments, sands and muds in the subtidal zone, creating discrete communities distinct from the surrounding area (Holt et al., 1998; Kaiser and Williams, 2011). They contribute to the stabilisation of marine sediment, pelagic-benthic coupling, biodeposition, and marine habitat

heterogeneity and complexity (thereby, biodiversity) by increasing the relief of seabed topography and creating a three-dimensional structure that other species can shelter or live within and feed upon (Franz et al., 2019; Holt et al., 1998; Kaiser and Williams, 2011; Mainwaring et al., 2014; Sampaio et al., 2022). Biogenic habitats, therefore, have an association of fauna and flora often richer and more diverse than in surrounding areas (Holt et al., 1998). Filter-feeding biogenic reef forming species, such as mussels and oysters, also filter phytoplankton from the water column, helping to mitigate eutrophication (Asmus and Asmus, 1991; Kaiser and Williams, 2011; Sampaio et al., 2022).

Biogenic habitats have, however, been subjected to persistent and increasing synergistic stressors, including marine resource extraction, trampling, pollution (e.g., sewage, agricultural run-off, industrial waste), disease, coastal development, predation and extreme weather conditions increasing with climate change (Airoldi and Beck, 2007; Halpern et al., 2008; Mainwaring et al., 2014; Ricklefs et al., 2020; Sampaio et al., 2022). Collectively, these stressors have undermined

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ecological resilience and impaired the capacity of biogenic habitats to continue providing vital ecological services (Airoldi and Beck, 2007; Duarte, 2009; Franz et al., 2019; Halpern et al., 2008; Lotze et al., 2006; Mainwaring et al., 2014; Ricklefs et al., 2020; Sampaio et al., 2022).

While habitat loss estimates and commercial fishing records typically only span the last few decades, in some regions, estuarine and nearshore habitats were already severely/irrevocably degraded before the onset of scientific monitoring (Airoldi and Beck, 2007; Ricklefs et al., 2020; Thurstan et al., 2024). The management of native coastal biogenic habitats is generally not well informed by knowledge of their historical distribution, extent and relative condition (Airoldi and Beck, 2007; Kotta et al., 2017; Marine Scotland, 2021). By neglecting long-term declines, modern management and conservation regimes compromise the persistence and functionality of biogenic habitats (Airoldi and Beck, 2007; Firth, 2021; Lotze et al., 2006). Establishing ecosystem baselines and quantifying historical exploitation prior to the onset of scientific monitoring is therefore increasingly important, but proves challenging owing to the patchy nature of historical records, issues with data certainty and poor spatial resolution compared to modern data (Thurstan et al., 2024a). Studies focusing on historical changes to key biogenic habitats thus remain limited (Airoldi et al., 2009; Baden et al., 2021; Boström et al., 2011; Franz et al., 2019; Lotze et al., 2006; Pogoda, 2019; Thurstan et al., 2013, 2024b). Recent works by Thurstan et al. (2024; 2024b) detailed the degradation and loss of the habitat forming European flat oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) across Europe over the last few hundred years. Others have researched the historical distribution of and threats to blue mussel (*Mytilus edulis*) beds in Europe, predominantly in the Wadden Sea, across the last century, using aerial photographs, sediment profiles, field surveys and archived publications (Baden et al., 2021; Büttger et al., 2014; Herlyn et al., 2008; Hertweck and Liebezeit, 2002; Millat and Herlyn, 1999; Nehls and Thiel, 1993). However, data on the historical distribution and extent of Scottish blue mussel beds, prior to the 20th century, is still lacking (Marine Scotland, 2021).

Due to the longevity of economic and cultural importance of blue mussels in Scotland, they are well represented in historical sources such as government enquiries, fisheries reports and surveys, and popular media from the late 18th century onwards. Interrogating such sources provides an opportunity to build an understanding and fill knowledge gaps on their historical value, distribution and decline. Note that mussel-dominated coastal shell middens in Scotland suggest that mussels have been exploited for thousands of years for food and bait (Fenton, 1992; Noble et al., 2018), therefore historical descriptions of mussel beds cannot be interpreted as representing an entirely pristine baseline. However, the mapping of historical habitats with available data provides critical perspective and context for setting future restoration and conservation goals by identifying areas of loss, the magnitude of loss, and areas with potential for recovery, especially in locations where the habitat, or patches of the habitat, still exist today (Thurstan et al., 2013).

This study aims to reconstruct the history of Scotland's mussel fishing industry and to establish the historical distribution, extent and condition of blue mussel bed habitat. Using archival records, we assess the timing, magnitude and reported drivers of mussel bed decline and compare historical and contemporary evidence to estimate the extent of habitat loss and highlight areas with potential for recovery. We further examine long-term trends in mussel and line fishing landings from the late 19th century to evaluate the development and eventual collapse of these once culturally and economically valuable interdependent industries. Finally, we assess the ecological and socio-economic consequences of prolonged exploitation on local marine ecosystems and dependent fishing communities. We hypothesise that blue mussel beds in Scotland were historically more widespread and extensive than present; mussel bed decline was driven by anthropogenic pressures, particularly intensive harvesting; and areas subject to prolonged exploitation show limited evidence of recovery following cessation of fishing effort, indicating long-term reductions in habitat resilience.

2. Methods

2.1. Data sources

A variety of historical sources spanning over three centuries, from 1760 to 1970, were systematically searched for quantitative and qualitative information referencing Scottish blue mussel beds and fisheries. Information collected was based on certain inclusion criteria; relevant sources included information on one or more of the following: the uses of mussels, fishing or cultivation techniques, descriptions of locations and extent, descriptions of natural/anthropogenic impacts, the condition of the beds, the competition over resources and the introduction of policies or management initiatives. Relevant extracts found across the sources were transcribed in an excel spreadsheet.

2.1.1. Government inquiries, investigations, resolutions & fisheries reports

Government inquiries and investigations (n = 6) were read in full and information on mussel fisheries or beds or impacts were extracted: The Sea Fisheries of the United Kingdom (Royal Commission, 1866), Trawl Net and Beam Trawl Fishing (Royal Commission, 1885), Mussel Beds in Tidal Waters (Scotland) (House of Commons, 1887), The Scottish Mussel and Bait Beds (Royal Commission, 1889), Investigations in relation to the fishing industry of the United Kingdom (Committee on Fishery Investigations, 1908), and The Condition of the Inshore Fisheries (Board of Agriculture and Fisheries, 1914). Inquiries pointed to several 'Fishery Board for Scotland' annual fisheries reports (n = 4) that contained reports on mussel beds: Second (1883), Sixth (1887), Tenth (1891), Eleventh (1892). All reports were sourced from 'ProQuest U.K. Parliamentary Papers' (<https://parlipapers.proquest.com/>). Scottish admiralty charts dating between 1795 and 1963 from the National Library of Scotland online repository were screened (National Library of Scotland, n.d.), but did not yield any data on mussel beds.

2.1.2. News articles

The British Newspaper Archive (<https://www.britishnewspaperarchive.co.uk/>) online repository was searched using the search term 'mussel'; the time-period 1750–1970 was selected, as was the 'Scotland' country filter; this returned n = 67,156 articles. Articles were organised from most to least relevant. For each half-century bracket (e.g., 1800–1849), the first thirty pages of articles (n = 360 articles) were screened, after which articles were found to be either not relevant or duplicates of earlier articles, thus, in total, n = 1678 articles were screened. Of these, n = 194 articles contained relevant information based on the inclusion criteria, spanning the years 1761–1969.

2.1.3. Books

Calderwood (1895) produced a popular book, 'Mussel Culture and the Bait Supply' for the purpose of raising awareness of the 'wasteful and ruinous' treatment of the Scottish mussel beds and the 'need for an increased supply of bait for the line fishers in the late 19th century. It contained chapters on the supply and demand of bait, the past and present mussel beds of Scotland, the natural history of mussels, cultivation methods and trials, and legal aspects (i.e., the need for and introduction of fishery regulations).

2.2. Spatial data

The methodology used here was adapted from a previous study on the historical distribution and extent of European oyster reefs by Thurstan et al. (2024, 2024b). Locations of mussel beds were extracted from the historical sources and cross-referenced between sources. Note that mussel beds were defined as areas of at least 5 m² (5 × 10⁻⁴ ha) (Marine Scotland, 2017). For n = 5 locations, descriptions mentioned 'beds' or 'various beds' without defining a number; due to lack of certainty, we only attributed one bed to each of these locations. Locations were mostly estimated from qualitative descriptions; in some cases, these were

detailed, in others, only cursory descriptions were given, e.g., beds were named after a coastal town, miles from shore, or occurring in a Loch (Scottish term for lake or sea inlet), river mouth, bay or harbour; as such, locations were assigned to 5 km² grid cells. In instances where historical place names were replaced with modern names, we cross-checked with historical maps to identify the location. In some cases, it was possible to improve the certainty of the location of the mussel beds from the description of the associated fishery. For example, beds could be identified as being intertidal or in a channel depending on the method of extraction, i.e., for intertidal beds, descriptions included people wading and collecting mussels by hand or by raking, for beds in deeper channels, mussels were taken by dredges. Locations were also established from mapped areas of Montrose (Source: *Dundee Advertiser*, 'Montrose Mussel Beds', 1899) and the Firth of Clyde (Source: Tenth Annual Report of the Fishery Board for Scotland, 1891), here, the location of mussel beds could be identified to a higher resolution; see [Appendix A](#) for map images. The digitising and spatial visualisation of Scottish blue mussel beds was completed in QGIS software v. 3.34.14 ([QGIS Development Team, 2023](#)). Locations were plotted as point data.

Extent data were also extracted from the written record. Qualitative reports of bed extent e.g., lengths, widths and areas, were converted into hectares. Where a range of measurements (e.g., lengths/widths) were given, a mean value was assigned. We mapped the known extent of mussel beds as proportional circles in QGIS. In some locations (n = 3),

extent information was given for an entire mussel fishing area that likely comprised of multiple beds, e.g. "In the estuary of the Tay there is a large mussel fishery extending from 8 to 10 miles in length by about 1 1/3 miles in breadth" (*Mid-Lothian Journal*, 'Mussel Beds in the Forth', 1887). Mussel bed extent data were compared to modern surveys of Scottish blue mussel beds by Marine Scotland ([Marine Scotland, 2017, 2020, 2021](#)).

2.3. Categorising the status of mussel beds

Qualitative data from the historical sources were used to categorise the status of the mussel beds: green = stable or increasing condition was reported, amber = declining condition, red = poor condition, black = destroyed. These were decided based on criteria given in [Table 1](#). Where multiple accounts were given for the same mussel bed, all available descriptions were considered in assigning their status, but more recent descriptions were prioritised. In cases where mussel beds were identified but no specific description of their condition was given (the case for n = 48 beds, 39 %), we used descriptions of the condition of the general mussel fishing area that these beds were in to assign them a status.

2.4. Fisheries landings

Annually resolved Scottish mussel landings and line fishing landings

Table 1

Criteria for assigning mussel beds a status, and examples of quotes demonstrating the kind of descriptions used to classify and assign statuses.

Status	Criteria	Example Quotes
Green	Low/sustainable level of exploitation: mussel beds abundant or producing increasing yields of mussels	"Almost inexhaustible [mussel bank]", "they have been on the increase" [Leith, 1864, 1889] "Mussels are found in great abundance" [Loch Caolisport, 1887] "So plentiful has been the crop of mussels lately, that after local demand was satisfied, quantities have been sent to other places" [South Esk, 1916]
Amber	Medium-high level of exploitation: mussel beds producing smaller yields/nearly exhausted	"Used to be a good mussel bed...it has fallen off very much" [Loch Etive, 1887] "Used to be plenty of them... but they are now nearly exhausted" [Loch Ryan, 1887] "Persons...were carrying off not only the mussels but the beds, including the spawn or brood; that in a short time the supply of bait would be totally lost" [Musselburgh, 1849]
Red	Unsustainable high level of exploitation: mussel beds nearly entirely exhausted/destroyed (also due to or exacerbated by other natural/anthropogenic pressures)	"Fishermen...some years ago removed the mussels in vast quantities without any regard to the destruction of the seed, and the bed is now practically exhausted" [Tynningham sands, 1899] "They were pretty well drawn off for 8 years, but the beds seem to be very exhausted, and all the mature mussels carried away" [Tain, 1889]
Black	Beds entirely taken-up, or destroyed by other natural/anthropogenic causes (e.g., predation, shifting sands/sand deposits, pollution)	"The fishermen came from Lerwick with high water- shoved down their dredges and just hauled up the whole scalp" [Weisdale, Shetland, 1928] "various mills erected on the river produced such pollution of the water that the mussels were destroyed" [Aberdour, Firth of Forth, 1889] "There is a deep water natural scalp, but in the present lease they were entirely destroyed by starfish" [Loanmore, Dornoch Firth, 1889]

were extracted from annual government fisheries reports. Sea Fisheries Statistical Reports from the Fishery Board for Scotland were available from the 'ProQuest U.K. Parliamentary Papers' online repository (years 1882–1921) (<https://parlipapers.proquest.com/>) and the Scottish Government website (years 1922–2020) (<https://www.gov.scot/collectio ns/sea-fisheries-statistics/>). Landings data recorded in 'cwts' (long hundredweight: British imperial system) were converted to tonnes using the conversion: 1cwt = 0.0508 tonne. Data were available from 1883 for Scottish mussel landings, and from 1892 for Scottish line fishing landings.

Line fishing and mussel landings data were first assessed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test in R (R Core Team, 2023; Shapiro and Wilk, 1965). As neither dataset was normally distributed and normality could not be achieved through transformation, relationships between mussel and line fishing landings were tested using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, a non-parametric method that does not assume normality and is appropriate for assessing monotonic relationships in historical fisheries data. Correlations were computed using the 'cor.test' function in R (R Core Team, 2023). To assess long-term temporal trajectories in landings, we tested for the presence of significant monotonic trends over time. Scottish mussel landings and line fishing landings data were preliminarily tested for autocorrelation using the Durbin Watson (DW) test (Durbin and Watson, 1950) ('tseries' package). Both time-series exhibited strong positive autocorrelation (DW = 0.1), violating the independence assumption of standard trend tests. We therefore used the modified 'Hamed and Rao (1998) Variance Correction Approach' Mann-Kendall trend test (mmkh) ('modifiedmk' package) which adjusts for serial correlation, preventing inflated significance and providing robust inference of long-term trends (R Core Team, 2023).

2.5. Area of Mussel beds exploited

We were able to estimate the area of mussel beds exploited through conversion factors given in the historical written sources and Scottish mussel landings data. A news article (St. Andrews Citizen, 'Ancient Industry- History of the mussel scalps', 1954) quoted regarding the local mussel fishery, that 1 basket of mussels = one square yard of mud bank. The Scottish Mussel and Bait Bed inquiry (Royal Commission, 1889) provided a conversion factor of baskets of mussels to tonnes: 104,000 baskets = 3470 tonnes. ∴ 1 basket = 0.033 tonnes. In another article (St. Andrews Citizen, 'Mussel Scalps', 1893), it was stated that between 64 and 108lbs (0.029–0.049 tonnes) of mussels = one square yard. We took an average of the three weights given to come up with the conversion factor of 0.037 tonnes of mussels = one square yard of mud bank exploited. This figure was multiplied by the annual mussel landings to estimate the total annual area of mussel beds extracted in Scotland from 1883 onwards.

3. Results

3.1. Historical analysis

3.1.1. Uses

Documentary sources suggest that blue mussel beds were highly valued and exploited in Scotland from at least the 16th century (St. Andrews Citizen, 'The Eden Mussel Scalps-Stormy History of Unique Industry', 1948). Whilst there is evidence to suggest that mussels were used as mineral resources for construction in the latter 18th century and for manure (i.e. fertiliser) across the 19th century, they were primarily said to be exploited on a large-scale to provide bait for line fishing (for whitefish species such as haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*) and cod (*Gadus morhua*)), and to a lesser extent, for food (Fig. 1). Of the 50,000 line fishers active in the late 19th century Scotland, nearly all used mussels for bait (Royal Commission, 1889). Calderwood (1895) estimated that in the 1890s over 42,000 miles of lines were deployed annually with approximately 47-million hooks that needed to be baited,

Fig. 1. Reported uses of blue mussels in Scotland and the number of times and range of dates these uses were referenced in historical source extracts. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

usually with two mussels per hook, equating to ~100 million mussels required every time all lines were in use.

Collecting, shelling and baiting hooks represented an immense amount of labour that entire fishing families participated in (John O' Groats Journal, 'Consumption of mussels for bait', 1872; Royal Commission, 1889):

"The very children themselves, as soon as they are able to crawl amongst the rocks to gather mussels for bait, they must do so [...] about twenty little girls, some not exceeding eight years of age, coming in from Portobello [Edinburgh] [...] each had a basket full of mussels on her back, tired and exhausted [...] those girls had left their homes that morning about three o'clock, in quest of these mussels" – John O' Groats Journal, 'Deep sea fishing', 1846

3.1.2. Expansion of bait and line fishing industries

In the early 1800s, the supply of mussel bait-in view of the number of fishers-seemed inexhaustible (Calderwood, 1895). However, rising demand for fish to cater for growing urban populations facilitated the expansion of Scotland's line fishing industry across the 19th century. Coupled with the introduction of lining from steam powered boats and increased ease of transporting catches on the growing railway network, a rising demand for mussel bait fuelled increased pressure on bait beds. From the mid-19th century, government inquiries, books and articles regarding mussel beds came in quick succession, all highlighting the extermination or desperate state of accessible mussel beds around Scotland's coast after a period of excess indiscriminate, unregulated fishing effort (Calderwood, 1895):

"The management, or rather mismanagement, of the mussel scalps around our coasts [is] most deplorable, as it is also one of the most suggestive chapters in the history of our fisheries, and forcibly illustrates the evil effects resulting from the absence of judicious regulations [...] with the expansion of the fishing industry the demand became greater, the run upon them increases, and soon assumed the character, in many cases, of reckless and wholesale destruction. Large parts of the beds were cleared bare, no discrimination was exercised between the young and the mature

mussels, and from the method of gathering them almost as many seem to have been trampled and destroyed as well as removed. In some parts of the country the small farmers near the seaboard were in the habit of making periodic raids upon them, removing cartloads to place upon their land as manure. The natural consequence of this improvidence and short sightedness on the part of fishermen and others is seen in the condition of the mussel beds today" - Aberdeen Press & Journal, 'The Scotch Mussel Fishery', 1888

Descriptions of a 'mussel bait famine' became widespread in news articles from the 1880s:

"The long-threatened mussel famine is within measurable distance [...] only paying the inevitable price for past improvidence and short-sightedness [...] Mussels are not a very delicate species; they will stand a good deal of rough usage and still survive and thrive. But even their endurance has a limit, and that limit has been already overstepped, with the result that we have at last received unmistakable warning that we must do one of two things- either treat mussels with more consideration and less neglect, or else be prepared to see them quit our inhospitable shores altogether [...] The rich Clyde beds from which some 4 or 5 thousand tons a year used to be obtained, are expected this year to provide the East Coast fishermen with no more than a few hundred tons of mussels large enough for bait [...] The demand for bait mussels has of course grown with the increase of line fishing [...] based on evidence gathered from the principal mussel beds, that unless large new scaups [mussel beds] are discovered, the supply of Scottish mussels suitable for bait during the present year will be only about 2/3rds of the quantity required by the fishermen [...] the supply will presumably be still smaller next year, and thus the fishermen are threatened with a serious crisis in their trade"- North British Daily Mail, 'A mussel famine', 1888

Scottish mussel bait fisheries well exemplified the tragedy of the commons (the over-exploitation of a shared resource (Hardin, 1968)), as individuals with access to the common resource all acted in their own interests and in doing so depleted it:

"Regretted that so important an industry should be allowed to drift out of existence for no other reason than it was nobody's business to attend to its development, and everybody's business to promote its extinction" - Greenock Herald, 'Mussel Fishing on the Clyde', 1888

3.1.3. Conflict

Rapid depletion of mussel beds was said to have led to mussel fisheries and fishing rights becoming among the most contentious coastal issues of the 18th and 19th centuries. Violent feuds over and raids on mussel fishing grounds occurred as towns fought over exclusive rights (Peterhead Sentinel, 'The Mussel Trade', 1885). Procurement of bait was described as a 'hereditary strife' among fishers of neighbouring villages while scarcity aggravated poaching activity (Calderwood, 1895):

"They [mussel beds] have had a stormy history of more litigation and contention than any other piece of seashore in the county [...] toward the end of the 18th century and the beginning of the 19th century they came to involve the town in lengthy and costly litigation. In 1765 it is recorded, for instance, that complaints had been received against the tenants of Earshall and Leuchars for taking a great number of cart loads of mussels from the mussel scalps at the Eden [...] So began a bitter feud between the townspeople [...] feelings ran high for the next forty years and in 1804 the town again went to law [...] the fisher people of St Andrews marched in a body and fell upon the people of the north bank and forcibly prevented them from taking the mussels. Fisher wives joined with their men in capsizing the rival boats and returning the mussels to the river"- St. Andrews Citizen, 'The Eden Mussel Scalps-Stormy History of Unique Industry', 1948

Those with access to mussel grounds monopolised these, with large fishing centres that did not have a local source facing a predicament

whereby they could pay high prices to import mussels from other regions or countries, raid beds nearby, or be prevented from going fishing for want of bait:

"Large tracts of the shore are quite devoid of mussel beds, and it is in these districts that some of the most important fishing communities are situated [...] for a distance of 150 miles, there are no local supplies of mussels to be obtained [...] [East coast fishers] complain not only of the difficulties of getting sufficient supplies of mussels, the boats sometimes prevented from going to sea for want of them, but also of the high prices they have generally to pay" -Aberdeen Press & Journal, 'The Scotch Mussel Fishery', 1888

3.1.4. Regulation

Attempts were made to regulate the Scottish mussel fisheries from the mid-19th century. The Mussel Fisheries (Scotland) Act, 1847, was passed to protect the beds-all mussels within a three-mile limit were vested in the Crown, meaning that those taking mussels from beds who had no right to take them could be charged with theft and prosecuted. Other regulations followed, for example, the 'Sea Fisheries (Clam and Bait Beds) Act, 1881, which aimed to protect bait beds from injury by beam trawlers (Calderwood, 1895), 'The Sea Fisheries Regulation (Scotland) Bill, 1892, which entitled the Scottish Fishery Board to acquire mussel fisheries and maintain, protect and regulate them for the benefit of the industry, and 'The Sea Fisheries Act', 1895, which empowered the Fishery Board to prohibit the dredging or taking of mussels by hand in the Firth of Clyde. More localised regulation efforts were also introduced in Musselburgh, in the form of permits required for mussel fishing and catch limits (Musselburgh News, 'Removal of mussels', 1935). The imposition of regulations that forced fishers to protect their own interests was widely anticipated:

"the fishermen are now anxious for state interference with regard to the regulation of the scalps, and will not hesitate to accept conditions which, being imposed on all alike, are framed for the improvement of the national bait supply" (Calderwood, 1895)

3.1.5. Death of industry

The bait and line fishing industries declined from the early 20th century, with historical sources proposing three main explanations. Firstly, the widespread destruction of mussel beds led to bait scarcity, increasing reliance on mussel imports, namely from Holland (Calderwood, 1895), and fuelling the development of new (bait-less) fishing techniques (Fenton, 1992). Second, the expansion of trawling and seining for whitefish in the latter 19th century rendered line fishing increasingly redundant, reducing the demand for bait (Board of Agriculture and Fisheries, 1914; Dundee Evening Telegraph, 'Broughty's Mussel Dredgers. Industry that is dying out', 1932). WW1 brought about a temporary revival of the bait and line fisheries, attributed to the withdrawal/sinking of steam trawlers and restrictions on fishing operations caused by enemy submarine activity, leading to increased reliance on small-boat line fishing using mussel bait (Buchan Observer, 'The Ythan mussel beds', 1915). Third, following WW1, abandoned fishing equipment had rotted/deteriorated, trawlers began to outcompete line fishers again and men were attracted to the relative security of other industries such as construction, while fewer women could or would bait lines (Dundee Evening Telegraph, 'Great days at the Ferryden fishing', 1950; Montrose Standard, 'The decline of fishing in Montrose and Ferryden', 1959).

After mussel gathering efforts subsided, there was a single account found in the news articles that highlighted the potential regenerative properties of mussel beds:

"Mussel gathering by local fishwives stopped some years ago and recently fishermen have been warning the town council that the beds might spread

to choke the entrance to Fisherrow Harbour." – The Scotsman, 'Mussel supplies', 1966

3.2. Blue mussel bed distribution

Blue mussel bed distributions and conditions were established from historical source extracts; most extracts ($n = 186$) were published between 1850 and 1900 (Fig. 2).

A conservative estimate of $n = 124$ beds in coastal Scottish waters were identified and mapped (Fig. 3); $n = 12$ broader fishing areas encompassing several beds were also described. Most of the identified beds were located on the east coast, namely in the Montrose basin ($n = 22$ beds), the Firth of Forth ($n = 17$ beds), the Firth of Tay ($n = 14$ beds), Dornoch Firth ($n = 10$ beds), Cromarty Firth ($n = 8$ beds) and the Beaully and Inverness Firths ($n = 7$ beds) (Fig. 3). The west coast of Scotland was more exposed to destructive storm and wave activity from the North Atlantic Ocean; beds were concentrated in the sheltered Firth of Clyde ($n = 20$) with others scattered around in nearby Lochs, in Oban and the Outer Hebrides (Fig. 3). Only $n = 6$ beds were identified in the Northern Isles, i.e., Orkney and Shetland (Fig. 3).

Descriptions of mussel bed conditions and key perceived drivers of these are outlined in Appendix B. The most prevalent threat to individual mussel beds and mussel fishing areas, mentioned in several accounts across the historical sources, was overfishing, ($n = 64$ beds were described as experiencing overfishing), with other stressors such as pollution ($n = 9$ beds), trawling activity ($n = 4$ beds) and natural causes such as shifting sands ($n = 15$ beds) and predation ($n = 14$ beds) also contributing to the poor condition of most beds (Fig. 3).

3.3. Status of beds

The majority ($n = 48$) beds were ascribed 'red' status, 42 with 'amber' status 19 'green' and 15 'black'. 'Green' beds were largely described as healthy due to low levels of exploitation, transplanting and cultivation efforts, and to restricted access by proprietors (Appendix B). 'Amber', 'red', and 'black' beds often suffered from cumulative natural and anthropogenic impacts such as overfishing of adult mussels, destructive fishing practices (dredging and taking or destroying 'spat' and young mussels), trampling, trawling activity, pollution (industrial waste and sewage), coastal development (construction/harbour works), storms and smothering by shifting sand/silt, and predation (predominantly by starfish and whelk species), to varying degrees (Appendix B). A common denominator of degraded sites was a lack of or failed management and cultivation effort.

Sources describing 'green' beds ranged from 1819 to 1932, with an

Fig. 2. Histogram showing the time-period of publication of historical record extracts used to map the historical distribution and describe the condition of blue mussel beds.

average year of 1886, sources describing 'amber' beds ranged from 1789 to 1958 (average year: 1892); sources describing 'red' and 'black' beds came later and stopped earlier than descriptions of green or amber beds, ranging from 1849 to 1930 (average year: 1887) and 1857–1928 (average year: 1890) respectively (Fig. 4). The mean year sources described the different conditions of beds spanned over only six years (1886–1892), which corresponds to the period over which most data sources were published (Fig. 2).

3.4. Blue mussel bed extent

Extent data were reported in the historical sources between 1887 and 1892 and were available for $n = 38$ (31 %) beds; the total described area of mussel beds equalled 1829 ha (Fig. 5). Individual mussel beds ranged from 0.008 to 777 ha (mean = 48 ha, median = 8 ha). Reported mussel fishing areas covered a much greater area, 5636 ha, with the largest reported areas in the Firth of Tay (~3108 ha), the Firth of Clyde (~1760 ha) and Cromarty Firth (~767 ha).

3.5. Comparison to modern data

A Marine Scotland commissioned review (Marine Scotland, 2017) suggests that blue mussel beds of significant extent are currently restricted to a few scattered locations in lochs and firths, including the Firth of Clyde, Dornoch Firth, Moray Firth, Firth of Tay, Solway Firth, Loch Creran, Loch Ailort, and Whiteness Voe in Shetland. Evidence for the presence of historical blue mussel beds in the Solway Firth, Loch Ailort and Whiteness Voe was not found in the historical sources. The persistence of beds in the Firth of Clyde, Dornoch Firth, Moray Firth, Firth of Tay and Loch Creran despite heavy historical exploitation at these locations (Figs. 3 and 5), is testament to their resilience to stressors. However, many have experienced major reductions in size, for example, several discrete mussel beds in the Dornoch Firth ranging from ~4 to 8 ha in the late 1880s (Fig. 5a) had decreased, with survey data suggesting only small <1 ha beds and isolated clumps of mussels remain (Cook et al., 2016; Marine Scotland, 2017). Furthermore, the largest known blue mussel bed in Scotland was identified in the survey as being in the Firth of Tay, reaching ~400 ha (Marine Scotland, 2017), however, the historical mussel fishing area here was reported to cover ~3110 ha (Mid-Lothian Journal, 'Mussel Beds in the Forth', 1887). Surveys suggest that blue mussel beds are still in decline in many locations around Scotland, with pronounced reductions in abundance and extent of blue mussels at 54 % of the 154 shore sites revisited between the early 2000s and 2015 (Burrows et al., 2017; Marine Scotland, 2020).

3.6. Fisheries landings

Mussel and line fishing landings exhibited large declines over the time-series: reported mussel landings decreased from ~13,800 tonnes in 1883 to 0 tonnes by 2004, while line fishing landings decreased from ~70,500 tonnes in 1892 to ~2400 tonnes in 2020, a decline of 96.6 % (Fig. 6). Mussel landings sharply increased over WW1, from ~4000 tonnes in 1913 to ~8400 tonnes in 1915 (increase of 111 %) and then decreased to ~4000 tonnes again by 1919 (Fig. 6). Mussel landings increased again from 1984, peaking in 1992 at around 3100 tonnes, before collapsing entirely by 2004. Line fishing landings marginally increased across the 2000s (Fig. 6). Strong statistically significant decreasing trends were evident over the mussel landings and line fishing landings time-series (mmkh, $\tau = -0.76$, $Z_c = -3.87$, $p = 1.1 \times 10^{-4}$, $n = 138$; mmkh, $\tau = -0.74$, $Z_c = -4.19$, $p = 2.8 \times 10^{-5}$, $n = 129$, respectively). Spearman's rank correlation analysis showed a strong significant positive correlation between the two variables ($\rho = 0.77$, $p < 0.001$).

3.7. Mussel fishing area exploited

From 1883 to 2003, approximately 1012 ha of mussel beds would

Fig. 3. Location and described condition of blue mussel beds in Scotland and associated natural/anthropogenic stressors, assigned from historical sources (1760–1970). Green points indicate mussel beds with stable or improving condition, amber points indicate beds in decline, red points indicate depleted beds in poor condition, and black points indicate beds that are entirely exhausted or destroyed. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Timeline showing the range of dates of historical status descriptions of blue mussel beds, and the mean year (grey marker) that beds were described/assigned a status. Green represents beds with stable or improving condition, amber represents beds in decline, red represents depleted beds in poor condition, and black represents beds that are entirely exhausted or destroyed. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Recorded extent (hectares) of Scottish blue mussel beds (1887–1892) shown as proportional circles (colour of circles represents status). Black squares represent beds with unknown areas of extent. Panels a–d are magnified: a) NE Scotland, b) Montrose basin, c) SE Scotland, d) Firth of Clyde. Circle sizes are consistent across panels. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

have been exploited to land a cumulative total of ~450,000 tonnes of mussels. The estimated mussel area exploited decreased by 93.9 %, from a maximum of 31 ha in 1883 to 2 ha in 2003.

4. Discussion

4.1. Historical exploitation of Scottish blue Mussel beds

Despite the ecological and historical socio-economic importance of blue mussel beds and fisheries in Scotland, the cumulative effects of anthropogenic disturbance and long-term habitat decline remain poorly understood. Historically, blue mussels formed extensive biogenic habitats that supported biodiversity, delivered key ecosystem services and sustained a productive fishery of importance to line fishers well into the 20th century, in addition to being harvested for farming and food. The historical evidence documents a transition from high densities of mussels covering expansive areas to effective extirpation in several regions. Between 1883 and 2003 nearly 500,000 tonnes of mussels were harvested from an estimated area of 1012 ha, and by circa 1930, over half of the 124 identified mussel beds in Scotland were described as nearly or entirely destroyed, with little written evidence of recovery after exploitation declined across the 20th century and ceased in 2004. These data illustrate the scale of anthropogenic impact and highlight that fisheries widely regarded as low impact can have lasting ecological consequences when targeting foundation species.

Our analysis found that blue mussels formed extensive beds and fishing areas covering nearly 7500 ha along Scotland's coastline and in firths and lochs in the 19th century (Fig. 4). This is, however, a substantial underrepresentation of true historical extent due to data limitations (only 31 % of beds had associated size data). The perceived abundance and regenerative capacity of mussels meant that conservation or cultivation was rarely considered (Fenton, 1992). Few regions,

viz. the Montrose basin and Eden estuary, instituted proactive management and cultivation approaches (i.e., the collection of juvenile mussel 'seed' and transplantation) (Holt et al., 1998; King, 1992; Mainwaring et al., 2014). Beds in these locations were generally described as being in better condition than those in un-managed regions (Appendix B), reflecting efforts to safeguard and increase mussel bait supplies. More localised regulatory efforts instituted in Musselburgh in

Fig. 6. Dual-axis time-series plot of Scottish mussel landings (grey line) and demersal line fishing landings (blue line) from 1883 and 1892 respectively, to 2020. The line fishing landings axis was scaled up from the mussel landings axis by 6. Spearman rank correlation analysis results are annotated. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

1935, e.g., catch limits and permits, were reactive to declines following indiscriminate take and raiding from the early 1800s. Following reduced fishing pressure, beds in Fisherrow, Musselburgh were reported to have increased in size in the 1960s (The Scotsman, 'Mussel supplies', 1966). These exceptions were overshadowed by the reality mussel beds faced in many accessible locations around Scotland's coast; here they experienced a myriad of stressors including unregulated fishing, dredging, pollution, collateral damage from emerging trawling activity, smothering by sand and predation, resulting in widespread depletion. Of the 124 mussel beds identified, only 15 % of described beds experienced low levels of exploitation and/or produced increasing yields of mussels across the 19th and early 20th centuries; 12 % were ascribed 'black' status, i.e., entirely taken up/destroyed by 1928, and 39 % were ascribed 'red' status, i.e., nearly entirely exhausted by 1930 (Fig. 4). The largest bed described as being extirpated was ~86 ha, situated at the mouth of the River Irvine in the Firth of Clyde (Fig. 5) - with observers attributing destruction to pollution from nearby chemical works. The largest identified 'red' beds included those between Helensburgh and Dumbarton in the Firth of Clyde (~777 ha), in Granton (~160 ha) and Tynninghame sands (~65 ha) in the Firth of Forth, in the Tay (~132 ha), and in the Beaully channel (~52 ha) (Fig. 5) - all described as severely overexploited by indiscriminate fishing.

The decline of mussel bed habitat documented here is not unique to Scotland but reflects a widespread pattern across temperate coastal regions of Europe. Over the past fifty years, the overall extent and biomass of blue mussel habitat in the Northeast Atlantic is estimated to have declined by over 50 % (Baden et al., 2021; OSPAR, 2023). Substantial historical and recent losses have been reported from the Wadden Sea (Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands) and in Norway Sweden and France; these declines were driven by the cumulative effects of historical exploitation, nutrient enrichment, habitat modification, predation pressure, disease and climate-related stressors (Baden et al., 2021; de Paoli et al., 2015; Johansson et al., 2024; OSPAR, 2023; Ricklefs et al., 2020).

4.2. Monitoring gaps

Lack of regular monitoring and paucity of contemporary high-resolution data on blue mussel bed distribution and extent in Scotland, and across the North Atlantic more broadly, means that recovery or further decline of the habitat remains difficult to establish (Baden et al., 2021; Jones et al., 2000; Marine Scotland, 2021; Tillian et al., 2024). The mapping of blue mussel bed distribution, based on 'The European Marine Observation and Data Network' (EMODnet) and supplemented with expert opinion, was considered to contain insufficient data to be accurate (OSPAR, 2023). Similarly, in Marine Scotland's biogenic reef survey (Marine Scotland, 2021) conducted across eleven regions in Scotland between 2011 and 2018, seven of the regions were data deficient for blue mussels, the habitat was not recorded in three regions, and where data were available (for the Moray Firth region), blue mussel habitat was estimated to have declined by 99.5 %. This highlights the need for improved spatiotemporal monitoring effort and comparison of survey results with available historical data to quantify habitat loss and/or recovery trajectories up to the present day.

4.3. Ecological & socio-economic impacts

The exploitation and ensuing transformation of estuarine and near-shore environments likely facilitated cascading community shifts and declining ecosystem functioning. The loss of structurally complex mussel bed habitat leads to seabed homogenisation (the widespread restructuring/flattening of coastal seafloors), associated community biodiversity loss or collapse, increased dominance of algae, and reduced nutrient cycling and removal of excess nutrients from eutrophic systems (Burrows et al., 2017; Koivisto and Westerborn, 2010; Sampaio et al., 2022; Sorte et al., 2017). These ecological changes are accompanied by

substantial socio-economic repercussions. Intensive mussel exploitation led to significant declines in mussel landings, which strongly correlated with significant declines in line fishing landings from the late 19th century (Fig. 6). Thousands of households that had organised their lives for centuries around the daily demands of bait collection, cultivation, shelling, line baiting, fishing and selling catches, experienced profound change as mussel bait became scarce, modern fishing gears, e.g., trawls were adopted, trawlers destroyed lines and outcompeted line fishers for declining whitefish stocks, and men transitioned to wage work in towns, factories or oil rigs (King, 1992; Nadel-Klein, 2000; Thurstan et al., 2014). Aspects of cultural and traditional fishing heritage, intergenerational knowledge transfer and community cohesion were gradually lost as industrial engine-powered fishing increased and took precedence across the 20th century. The reorganisation and concentration of capital in powerful industrial fishing enterprises saw the near extinction of many fishing dependent communities in Scotland after WW1; where high densities of occupationally exclusive fishing towns around Scotland's coast once subsisted on bait and line-fishing proceeds, few such places remain (Nadel-Klein, 2000).

The results of this study suggest that the extensive exploitation of Scottish mussel beds across the 19th and into the 20th century was driven primarily by demand for bait for use by line fishers. This narrative contrasts to the prevailing view that a static gear (line) fishery has comparatively little collateral impact on benthic habitats and the persistence of foundational biogenic reef forming species (Grabowski et al., 2014; Rouxel, 2017), e.g., compared to bottom trawling (Sciberras et al., 2018), as it ignores the indirect repercussions of bait extraction to feed these fisheries. The historical exploitation of ecologically vital habitat forming species for bait using a variety of fishing techniques with varying levels of invasiveness (dredging, raking and hand collecting) exposes an under-researched issue concerning the sustainability of line fisheries, with results highlighting that the impacts on target bait species and wider ecosystems were profound. Collie et al. (2000) and Kaiser et al. (2003) found that inter-tidal dredging had a greater initial adverse effect on benthic biota compared to trawling. The ecosystem effects of commercial bait collection and impacts on target species are poorly addressed in the literature as these fisheries are perceived as low value, data-limited and unregulated (Watson et al., 2017); research is mainly focused on the impact of bait collecting for recreational and artisanal line fisheries (McPhee et al., 2002; Meyer et al., 1999; Simon et al., 2021; Watson et al., 2017). Furthermore, few studies have explored the development of new bait types to replace commercially valuable traditional longline bait species due to lack of research on fish search behaviour for food (Løkkeborg et al., 2014).

4.4. Mussel aquaculture

Mussel aquaculture, coupled with the decline of commercial mussel bait fisheries, has helped relieve pressure on remnant natural beds amid rising consumer demand since the latter 20th century (Dias et al., 2011; Edwards, 1997). Scotland's mussel rope aquaculture production expanded from the 1980s to the early 2000s, with yields increasing from hundreds to thousands of tonnes (Dias et al., 2009). This rise of production coincided with the brief revival of Scotland's mussel fishery, with mussel landings ranging between ~300 and ~3000 tonnes from the mid-1980s to 2003 (Fig. 6). It is likely that increases in Scottish mussel landings over this period were driven by demand for juvenile mussels (spat) for mussel culture (Dias et al., 2011; Seafish, n.d.). However, mussel aquaculture operations across Europe have since gone into decline due to limited mussel spat availability, disease, climate change (and associated ocean acidification, sea level rise, and rises in harmful algal blooms), and low profitability (Avdelas et al., 2021), underscoring the ongoing vulnerability of blue mussel populations and fisheries.

4.5. Habitat conservation & restoration

In recent years, halting biodiversity loss and reversing ecosystem degradation has risen high on the agenda of policy makers (EU, 2020; Hermoso et al., 2022). There is a growing impetus to restore native biogenic habitats that have undergone significant declines, due to their conservation value, i.e., their integral contribution to biodiversity enrichment and the provision of ecosystem services (zu Ermgassen et al., 2020). Scope for restoration has been assisted by conservation designations e.g., blue mussel beds are identified as a Habitat of Principal Importance and a Priority Marine Feature under the Marine (Scotland) Act, 2010, with some beds now a protected feature within MPAs (Mainwaring et al., 2014; Marine Scotland, 2017). Blue mussel beds in Scotland are also on the OSPAR list of threatened and declining habitats owing to the severity of historical anthropogenic impact (OSPAR, 2023). However, legal protection alone is not necessarily sufficient to allow the recovery of the habitat, if historical or new driving factors of their decline remain present, e.g., pollution, disease, harmful algal blooms, predation, competition with invasive species (e.g., the pacific oyster (*Crassostrea gigas*)) and poor weather (Avdelas et al., 2021; Herlyn et al., 2008). Adopting ecosystem-based management approaches will be pivotal as these aim to manage whole ecological units by comprehensively addressing terrestrial and sea-based human and environmental impacts (Eriksson et al., 2010; Slocombe, 1993).

Nature-based solution approaches, such as mussel bed cultivation (i.e., supporting the growth and survival of mussel beds through spat collection and seeding), mussel transplantation (i.e., relocating mussel spat from donor sites to restore degraded or extirpated mussel beds) and integration of mussel aquaculture into estuarine and coastal areas, provide relatively low-cost, practical strategies for enhancing ecosystem functioning, shoreline resilience, water quality, carbon burial, biodiversity and fishery yields (Cranford et al., 2012; Islam et al., 2024; Koplin et al., 2025; Mascorda-Cabre et al., 2024). Herlyn et al. (2008) found that blue mussel larvae prefer to settle in sites of present mussel beds or sites with bases of former mussel beds with dead shell material, if suitable abiotic conditions prevail, as these areas provide hard substrata for settlement. Historical distribution data and presence of dead shell material can therefore guide site selection for habitat restoration.

5. Conclusions

This study draws on over three-hundred historical records published between the late 1700s and 2000s to reconstruct the historical distribution, extent and scale of exploitation of blue mussel beds in Scotland. Between 1883 and 2003, nearly half a million tonnes of mussels were extracted from an estimated area of 1012 ha. We identified 124 mussel beds historically in existence around Scotland's coast covering a conservative estimate of 1830 ha, 51 % of which were classified as highly exploited or entirely destroyed—primarily for bait-by the early 1900s. The extent to which mussel bed habitats have recovered following the decline and eventual cessation of commercial bait fishing remains uncertain due to a lack of modern data. While line fishing is considered a comparatively low-impact method for targeting finfish, our findings demonstrate that indirect pressures associated with bait extraction can exert substantial and long-lasting effects on foundation species and the ecosystems they support.

Given the absence of systematic long-term monitoring of coastal habitats, the archival data used here provides a rare opportunity to visualise the widespread decline or destruction of blue mussel beds in Scotland before the onset of modern surveying, to identify key anthropogenic and natural drivers behind their decline, and to quantify the development and collapse of once culturally and economically integral local mussel and line fishing industries. Quantifying the magnitude of historical exploitation is critical for interpreting the current degraded state of coastal biogenic habitats and provides invaluable context for habitat and biodiversity restoration initiatives.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zoe F.J. Heard: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Callum M. Roberts:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Ruth H. Thurstan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Statements and declarations

The work described has not been published before, and it is not under consideration for publication anywhere else.

The publication has been approved by all coauthors.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2025.109694>.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study will be available in Figshare using the identifier: 10.6084/m9.figshare.29931434.

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